

A Systemic Approach to social media and pre-adolescents through thinking skills education

The day has come!

Exploring the ASAP Learning Units: 6 paths to critical thinking

In the framework of the ASAP Educational Programme, we have developed six Learning Units that support preadolescents, and all the learning community, in building critical thinking, media literacy, and social competences for the digital age. Each unit addresses a key challenge that children face when growing up with social media and offers creative tools for reflection, dialogue, and growth.

In this issue, you can discover six short articles that present the Learning Units — from *Role Models* to *Authenticity & Authority*. Each article explores what the unit contains, why it matters, and how it helps kids and adults become more resilient and responsible digital citizens.

Authenticity & Authority: learning to recognise reliable information

How can we tell what's true online? This unit equips students with fact-checking skills and critical awareness to recognise reliable sources and fight misinformation.

[Read more](#)

Communication: building bridges with empathy and assertiveness

Words can build bridges or walls. This unit trains preadolescents in empathy, active listening, and assertiveness to improve both real-life and digital communication.

[Read more](#)

Emotions: understanding feelings in the Digital Age

Likes, comments, and posts trigger feelings. This unit helps children name, understand, and manage emotions, building empathy and resilience online and offline.

[Read more](#)

Onlife: navigating the space between online and offline

Online and offline are now one life. Through this unit, students explore their digital routines, footprints, and responsibilities as conscious digital citizens.

[Read more](#)

The Power of Questions: learning to think critically and curiously

Curiosity is a superpower. This unit teaches children how to ask meaningful questions, distinguish facts from opinions, and use inquiry to foster dialogue.

[Read more](#)

Role Models: the learning from the figures who inspire US

Who do kids admire, and why? This Learning Unit helps preadolescents reflect on the figures who inspire them and connect admiration with positive values.

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